

References

1. P. S. FERNANDES and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1059.
2. P. S. FERNANDES, V. V. NADKARNY, G. A. JABBAR and R. P. JANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 840.
3. K. C. JOSHI and D. S. NEHTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 613.
4. R. CREMLYN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968 (c), 11.
5. M. SHAH, C. T. BHATT and D. D. KANGA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1375.
6. P. S. FERNANDES, R. D' COSTA and V. V. NADKARNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 738.

Chemical Constituents of *Polypodium amoenum* Wall

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POLYPODIUM amoenum (Polypodiaceae) grow in the Himalayan region at an altitude 4,000-11,000 ft and also from Garhwal to Bhutan, very common in Khasia range (altitude 3,000-6,000 ft). The present communication describes the isolation of fern-9(11)-ene²⁻³, hop-22(29)-ene⁴⁻⁶ and β -sitosterol from the whole plant.

Benzene extract of the dried powdered fern was separated into acid and neutral fractions. The latter was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petrol (60-80°) yielded a waxy solid which was found by TLC (12% AgNO₃ impregnated silicagel) to be a mixture of two components. On rechromatography over silicagel (E. Merck) impregnated with AgNO₃ followed by crystallisation (chloroform : methanol) it afforded two hydrocarbons A and B having the same mol. formula C₃₀H₅₀(M⁺410).

Compound A (found C, 88.01, H, 12.15) m.p. 166-68° [α_D]CHCl₃ - 16.1° showed significant peaks at m/e 257, 243, 231 in its mass spectrum similar to those recorded for fern-9(11)-ene. Its identity was established by comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p., IR and Co-TLC).

Compound B (found C, 87.59, H, 12.42), m.p. 210-11°, [α_D]CHCl₃ + 61°. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 880 cm⁻¹ (>C=CH₂) was found to be identical (m.m.p., IR, MS) with hop-22(29)-ene (Diploptene).

Further elution of the column with petrol : benzene (3 : 2) furnished β -sitosterol, m.p. 133-36°, [α_D]CHCl₃ - 32°, acetate, m.p. 126-28°, [α_D]CHCl₃ - 38°, identical with authentic specimens.

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References

1. C. B. CLARKE 'A Review of the ferns of Northern India' Reprinted by B. SINGH, M. P. SINGH, Dehra Dun and Periodical Experts, Delhi, 1978, 550.
2. H. AGETA, K. IWATA and S. NATORI, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1963, 1447.
3. H. AGETA and K. IWATA, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1966, 6069.
4. H. AGETA, K. IWATA and S. NATORI, *Tetrahedron letters* 1964, 3413.
5. Y. TSUDA, K. ISOBE, S. FUKUSHIMA, H. AGETA and K. IWATA, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1967, 23.
6. H. AGETA, K. IWATA and K. YONEZAWA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull (Tokyo)*. 1968. 408.

Coumarins from *Pimpinella diversifolia*

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P. diversifolia (Umbelliferae) is a herb growing in the north-western Himalayan region. No work on this plant has so far been reported. From the aerial parts of this plant two coumarins have been isolated and identified as ammirin (isoangomalin) and oxypeucedanin on the basis of IR, NMR, MS and TLC data.

The petroleum ether extract of the air dried, powdered aerial parts (2 Kg) of the plant yielded a dark green residue (30 g) which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (grade IV). Elution with petroleum ether gave a mixture of hydrocarbons, m.p. 77-78°. The earlier benzene eluates on chromatography over silica gel followed by PLC afforded ammirin (44 mg) in needles (benzene-acetone), m.p. 110-12° (lit.², m.p. 117°), blue fluorescence under UV. NMR (90 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.79(3H, s, methyl), 3.27 (2H, dq, J 16, 8Hz, H-3'), 4.98(1H, br s) and 5.13 (1H, br s)-olefinic protons, 5.32 (1H, t, J 8Hz, H-2'), 6.23 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-3), 6.78 (1H, s, H-8), 7.30 (1H, s, H-5), 7.62 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-4). MS : Ion peaks at m/e 228 (M⁺), 213, 185 among others.

Later fractions of benzene eluates from silica gel chromatography, on purification by PLC, afforded oxypeucedanin (20 mg), m.p. 144-45° (lit.³ m.p. 142-43°), M⁺ 286. IR and NMR spectra were in concordance with those of an authentic sample.

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